

Evaluating Gabapentin and Pregabalin Efficacy in Treating Neuropathic Pain from Peripheral Nerve Injury

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Abstract:

Background and Aim: Both gabapentin and pregabalin have been demonstrated to be effective in the treatment of diabetic peripheral neuropathy and post herpetic neuralgia. In order to evaluate the efficacy of pregabalin and gabapentin in the treatment of neuropathic pain at a government tertiary care hospital in India, the current study was conducted.

Material and Methods: Pregabalin was administered to 50 patients, while gabapentin was administered to the remaining 50. The Douleur Neuropathique 4 questionnaire (DN4) was employed to diagnose patients with neuropathic pain. The efficacy of the substance was determined by its ability to reduce neuropathic pain at consistent intervals.

Results: The mean pain rating score of group 1 and group 2 is 7.92 and 7.95, respectively, on the first day of OPD (baseline). There is no significant difference between the two groups. However, the pain rating of group 1 is significantly different from that of group 2 (gabapentin) at the fourth week, as evidenced by the two-tailed test. ($p < 0.05$) In the same vein, group 1 (pregabalin) is statistically significantly more efficacious than group 2 (gabapentin) at the 12th week. ($p < 0.05$) In the same vein, group 1 (pregabalin) is more efficacious than group 2 (gabapentin) at the 24-week mark, with a statistical significance level of 0.001.

Conclusion: The study determined that pregabalin is a superior medication for the treatment of neuropathic pain compared to gabapentin. However, the results of the current study may require further validation in a larger sample size.

Keywords: Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy, Gabapentin, Neuralgia, Pregabalin.

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Introduction

Neuropathic pain, also known as NP, is characterized by pain that arises from issues with the nervous system, such as dysfunction, disease, or damage. [1] Various factors can contribute to the development of NP, including diabetes mellitus, neoplasia, surgery, spinal-cord injury, stroke, multiple sclerosis, and traumatic nerve injury. [2] The development of NP involves the release of inflammatory mediators after tissue trauma, leading to the sensitization of nociceptors in the peripheral region.

After nociceptors are sensitized, they become more responsive to stimulation, leading to an increase in spinal cord activity known as "windup." This can potentially prolong the pain, and if left untreated, may lead to central sensitization and chronic neuropathic pain. [3-5] Typical clinical symptoms of neuropathic pain include allodynia, hyperalgesia, electrical and shooting pain, and spontaneous burning pain. The DN4 questionnaire is commonly utilized in outpatient departments as a screening

tool for diagnosing neuropathic pain. Common clinical symptoms of NeP include allodynia, hyperalgesia, electrical and shooting pain, and sudden searing pain. Dealing with NeP can be quite burdensome, as it not only causes physical discomfort but also takes a toll on mental well-being, ultimately affecting one's overall quality of life. Neuropathic pain affects neurons in various brain regions involved in sensory perception, emotions, thinking, information processing, and pain modulation. There is often a connection between NeP and depression, indicating that changes in these regions may lead to changes in behaviour. [6-8]

According to a recent meta-analysis, it has been found that the prevalence of pain with neuropathic features is estimated to be between 6.9% and 10%. [9] Neuropathic pain management is categorized into various treatment options, each with its own level of utilization and acceptance. Medications are essential for treating neuropathic pain, serving as

the primary and secondary treatment options. Tricyclic antidepressants (TCAs), serotonin norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs), gabapentanoids, tramadol, lidocaine, and capsaicin have been found to be highly effective options. [10-12]

Pregabalin and gabapentin fall under the category of gabapentinoids. These medications belong to a group of anticonvulsants that function by restricting the release of neurotransmitters. They achieve this by obstructing presynaptic alpha-2-delta calcium channels in the dorsal horn. Multiple international societies recognize them as the go-to treatment for neuropathic pain. [13-15] These medications are highly regarded by numerous international societies as effective treatments for neuropathic pain. Both gabapentin and pregabalin have demonstrated effectiveness in treating post herpetic neuralgia and diabetic peripheral neuropathy.

Material and Methods

This study was conducted at a department of pharmacology in a Tertiary Care Teaching Institute in India over a period of one year. It was designed as a randomized, prospective, open-labeled study.

The patients were assessed based on their medical history, current symptoms, and previous symptoms. Patients with a diagnosis of neuropathic pain are seeking treatment at the outpatient department of medicine. Patients were enrolled in the study after signing the consent form, which was provided in multiple languages for their convenience. In the study, we compared two commonly used drugs, pregabalin and gabapentin. These medications were readily available at our tertiary care center where the study took place.

Pregabalin is a compound derived from gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) that has various therapeutic properties, including anti-convulsant, anti-epileptic, anxiolytic, and analgesic effects. It is still unclear how pregabalin works, but it specifically attaches to alpha-2-delta ($\alpha_2\sigma$) subunits of presynaptic voltage-dependent calcium channels (VDCCs) found in the central nervous system (CNS). When pregabalin binds to VDCC $\alpha_2\sigma$ subunits, it stops calcium from entering the cells and prevents the release of different neurotransmitters, such as glutamate, norepinephrine, serotonin, dopamine, and substance P. This inhibition of synaptic transmission leads to a decrease in neuronal excitability. Pregabalin does not directly bind to GABA-A or GABA-B receptors and does not affect GABA uptake or degradation. Pregabalin is a medication that helps to manage painful neuropathy and prevent seizures. Gabapentin is a synthetic analogue of the neurotransmitter gamma aminobutyric acid, known for its anticonvulsant properties. While the precise way in which

gabapentin works remains a mystery, it seems to have the ability to suppress the activity of excitatory neurons. This agent also has pain-relieving properties.

Diagnosing neuropathic pain involves using the Douleur Neuropathique en 4 questions and evaluating it with a numerical pain scoring scale. An article in the Korean Journal of Pain by Gudala et al has validated the Hindi version of the DN4 questionnaire. The DN4 questionnaire consists of seven items that assess symptoms and three items that evaluate clinical examination findings. It's incredibly user-friendly and has been translated into a wide range of languages. Reported findings indicate an 83% sensitivity and a 90% specificity, suggesting that the seven sensory descriptors can be reliably used as a self-report tool. The DN4 questionnaire is a widely used screening test for assessing neuropathic pain in everyday medical practice. The DN4 tool was developed by a group specializing in neuropathic pain from France. It aids in distinguishing between neuropathic pain and non-neuropathic pain.

Clinical scoring system

Signs and symptoms were observed at baseline and at 4th week, 12th week, and 24th week after treatment initiation, providing valuable information on the progress of the patients. The Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) is a tool used to assess pain intensity in adults. It provides a unidimensional measure of pain intensity. The NPRS is a numerical version of the visual analog scale (VAS) where individuals choose a whole number to represent the intensity of their pain. A popular choice is a horizontal bar or line. Just like the VAS, the NPRS is based on terms that describe the extremes of pain severity. The numeric scale used to measure pain ranges from '0' to '10', with '0' representing one extreme of pain and '10' representing the other extreme.

Statistical analysis

The data was compiled and entered into a spreadsheet computer program (Microsoft Excel 2019) and then exported to the data editor page of SPSS version 15 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). The quantitative variables were described using either means and standard deviations or median and interquartile range, depending on their distribution. The data for qualitative variables were displayed as counts and percentages. Confidence level and level of significance were set at 95% and 5% respectively for all tests.

Results

Patients with symptoms of neuropathic pain were invited to participate in the study conducted at the medicine OPD on specific days. A total of 100 patients who met the inclusion criteria and agreed

to participate were selected for the study. They were then randomly assigned to one of two groups.

According to our study, the average age of the population is 44.10 ± 15.25 . Group 1 (pregabalin) has an average age of 44.36 ± 15.22 , while group 2 (Gabapentin) has an average age of 43.91 ± 15.20 .

This suggests that the age distribution in these groups is similar. Among the 100 patients, there were 42 females (42%) and 58 males (58%). In group 1 (pregabalin), there were 18 females and 24 males. In group 2, there were 24 females and 34 males who were prescribed gabapentin.

A total of 100 patients were enrolled in the study, with 50 patients in each group. The signs and symptoms were evaluated at the 4th, 12th, and 24th week. Group 1 and group 2 showed similar pain

rating scores at the first day of OPD (baseline), with mean scores of 7.92 and 7.95 respectively. However, during the fourth week, there is a noticeable difference in pain ratings between group 1 and group 2 (Gabapentin), which is statistically significant (two-tailed). The p-value is less than or equal to 0.05. In the 12th week, it was found that group 1 (pregabalin) was more effective than group 2 (gabapentin) with a statistically significant difference. The statistical significance level was found to be less than or equal to 0.05. At the 24th week, it was found that group 1 (pregabalin) had a higher level of effectiveness compared to group 2 (gabapentin), with a statistically significant level of 0.001.

Table 1: Gender wise Distribution of study Population

Gender	Number	Percentage (%)
Male	58	58
Female	42	42
Total	100	100

Table 2: Comparing means between two groups at 4th week, 12th week and 24th week

Variable	Day 1	4 th week	12 th week	24 th week
Significance level of group means between pregabalin and gabapentin	0.10	0.001*	0.001*	0.001*

* Indicate statistically significance at $p \leq 0.05$

Discussion

When comparing the effectiveness of PGB and GBP in reducing pain severity in patients with Neuropathic pain, it was found that GBP outperformed PGB. In addition, regardless of the order in which they were taken, GBP was associated with a lower number and less intense adverse events.

Both PGB and GBP showed similar effectiveness in reducing pain-related impairment when compared directly. The drug's effectiveness was evaluated by measuring the reduction in neuropathic pain using a numerical pain rating scale at specific intervals. The cases were divided into two groups at random. Group 1, consisting of 50 participants, were administered a dosage of Pregabalin at 300 mg. Group 2, consisting of 50 individuals, were administered Gabapentin at a dosage of 600mg once a day for a duration of 24 weeks.

Our investigation revealed a significant decrease in numerical pain rating scores (NPRS) across all post periods in both groups, when compared to their respective predecessor periods. In each period, the mean numerical pain rating score (NPRS) showed a significant improvement in the group prescribed pregabalin compared to the group prescribed gabapentin. This suggests that pregabalin may be

more effective in reducing pain compared to gabapentin. According to the study, pregabalin has been found to be more effective than gabapentin in treating neuropathic pain. Treating NP can be a challenging task, regardless of its cause. Conventional analgesic therapies often fail to provide relief. [19,20] Non-conventional drugs, such as antidepressants, gabapentin, and pregabalin, have shown effectiveness in treating NP. Both gabapentin and pregabalin have analgesic effects by binding to the α -2- δ subunit of N-type voltage-gated calcium channels. When there is an increase in neuronal activity and damage to the nerves, the binding to this sub-unit can help decrease the release of excitatory neurotransmitters like glutamate and substance P. [21,22]

The findings suggest that gabapentin and pregabalin can be effective in treating NP, despite the fact that we still have limited understanding of how exactly they work as pain relievers. According to Attal et al's research, pregabalin has been shown to be more effective than gabapentin for patients with chronic neuropathic pain resulting from spinal cord injury. [23]

In a study conducted by Mishra et al, 120 patients were enrolled in a prospective randomized double-blind placebo-controlled trial. The aim was to compare the efficacy of amitriptyline, gabapentin, and pregabalin in relieving neuropathic cancer

pain. The results revealed that all three antineuropathic drugs demonstrated effectiveness in alleviating cancer-related neuropathic pain. [24]

There was a notable reduction in the use of morphine when using pregabalin to treat neuropathic cancer pain and symptoms, compared to other antineuropathic drugs. This finding is both statistically and clinically significant. In a recent publication, Kiss et al. provide a comprehensive overview and analysis of the latest national and international guidelines released within the past five years. [25] According to a study conducted by Robertson et al., the effectiveness and side effects of pregabalin were found to be superior to gabapentin in treating sciatica.

The researchers analyzed various papers to arrive at this conclusion. [26] According to a study conducted by Bruce C. M. Wang et al, pregabalin has been found to be an effective treatment for post herpetic neuralgia (PHN). The study utilized a simulation model customized for China and analyzed data from 1000 patients with PHN to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of pregabalin compared to gabapentin. [27] In a randomized, double-blind, cross-over trial conducted by Robertson et al., the effectiveness of pregabalin was compared to gabapentin in relieving pain for individuals with sciatica.

The study shed light on the various treatment options available and highlighted the efficacy of pregabalin. [26] In a case report by Kopel et al., Pregabalin was administered to a patient for PHN when gabapentin treatment proved ineffective. [27] After reviewing 11 studies, Robertson et al concluded that pregabalin is more effective than gabapentin in treating sciatic pain. They also considered the side effects of both medications. [26] In a recent study, Bruce C M Wang et al created a 12-week simulation model specifically tailored to China to assess the cost-effectiveness of pregabalin versus gabapentin in a group of 1000 patients with pNeP and PHN. Their findings suggest that pregabalin is a highly effective treatment option for post herpetic neuralgia. [28]

A number of randomized controlled trials have already reported on the effectiveness of pregabalin in providing relief from neuropathic pain and reducing sleep disturbances. These trials focused on patients with conditions such as painful diabetic neuropathy and postherpetic neuralgia. However, the present study stands out as the first to specifically investigate the efficacy of pregabalin in treating neuropathic pain resulting from traumatic peripheral nerve injury. [29-31]

According to the findings of this study, pregabalin proved to be effective in providing relief from neuropathic pain and minimizing sleep disturbances in individuals who have experienced

traumatic peripheral nerve injury. A case report was published by Kopel et al, detailing the treatment of a patient with PHN. The patient was initially treated with gabapentin, but after it proved ineffective, pregabalin was used instead. [27] Pregabalin has shown promising results as a first-line therapy for PHN and other types of neuropathic and chronic pain. A network meta-analysis was conducted by Tong et al, which analyzed eight randomized controlled trials investigating four different interventions. [32] According to the data on pain intensity after treatment, the effectiveness of the medications can be ranked from highest to lowest as follows: pregabalin, gabapentin, amitriptyline, carbamazepine, and placebo. This study specifically focused on patients with neuropathic pain related to spinal cord injury.

According to the study, the effectiveness of different medications for neuropathic pain in individuals with spinal cord injury was ranked in the following order: pregabalin, gabapentin, amitriptyline, carbamazepine, and placebo. This ranking was based on the average pain intensity experienced after treatment.

One important aspect to consider in this study are the limitations, such as the potential variation in pain perception among individuals. There is a possibility of statistical error in this study due to the small sample size, lack of blinding, or absence of a placebo group. Having larger sample sizes and conducting studies from multiple perspectives can greatly enhance the accuracy and reliability of the findings. For more comprehensive data, it is necessary to include larger groups and conduct longer follow-up periods.

Conclusion

The effectiveness of pregabalin 300 mg once daily surpassed that of gabapentin 600 mg administered once daily in terms of symptom and sign improvement. According to the study, pregabalin has been found to be more effective than gabapentin in treating neuropathic pain. However, it is important to note that further validation on a larger sample size may be necessary to confirm these findings.

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